

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANT AND FREE ENERGY DATA OF PHENETSAL COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND IONIC STRENGTHS IN ALCOHOL-WATER SYSTEM, (70 : 30 v/v)

Metal ion	Temp. °C	Ionic strength	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	-ΔG ₁ k cal/mole	-ΔG ₂ k cal/mole	-ΔG* k cal/mole
Mn ⁺⁺	25	0.00	5.52	5.18	10.70	7.53	7.06	14.59
		0.05	5.05	4.64	9.69	6.89	6.33	13.22
		0.10	4.89	4.01	8.90	6.67	5.47	12.14
		0.20	4.69	3.83	8.52	6.40	5.22	11.62
	35	0.10	4.44	3.63	8.07	6.26	5.12	11.38
	45	0.10	4.23	3.50	7.73	6.16	5.09	11.25
Co ⁺⁺	25	0.00	5.65	5.20	10.85	7.70	7.09	14.79
		0.05	5.22	4.78	10.00	7.12	6.29	13.41
		0.10	5.02	4.61	9.63	6.85	6.29	13.14
		0.20	4.82	4.42	9.24	6.57	6.03	12.60
	35	0.10	4.67	3.99	8.66	6.58	5.62	12.20
	45	0.10	4.50	3.72	8.22	6.55	5.41	11.96
Ni ⁺⁺	25	0.00	5.84	5.40	11.24	7.96	7.36	15.33
		0.05	5.49	4.90	10.39	7.49	6.68	14.17
		0.10	5.32	4.73	10.05	7.13	6.45	13.58
		0.20	5.10	4.32	9.42	6.95	5.89	12.84
	35	0.10	4.93	4.14	9.07	6.95	5.84	12.79
	45	0.10	4.86	3.96	8.82	7.07	5.76	12.53
Cu ⁺⁺	25	0.00	7.08	5.84	12.92	9.65	7.96	17.62
		0.05	6.22	5.07	11.29	8.48	6.91	15.40
		0.10	5.66	4.90	10.56	7.72	6.68	14.40
		0.20	5.35	4.52	9.87	7.30	6.16	13.46
	35	0.10	5.17	4.33	9.50	7.29	6.11	13.39
	45	0.10	5.00	4.16	9.16	7.28	6.07	13.33

*ΔG = ΔG₁ + ΔG₂.

References

- V. K. JAITLEY and B. S. PANNU, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1983, **60**, 109.
- V. K. JAITLEY, H. S. HOTHIA and B. S. PANNU, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1983, **62**, 369.
- J. B. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Hasse and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.
- M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
- H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 29A.
- A. G. STERRVIN, *Neth. Appl.*, 1965, **6**, 605, 517.
- L. G. VAN UITERT and C. G. HAAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
- H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
- H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746.

Physico-chemical Studies on Ag(I) Benzamidothiosemicarbazide Complex

R. D. KAUSHIK, SHREESH BHARDWAJ, M. N. ANSARI
and

M. C. JAIN

Department of Chemistry, S. D. College, Muzaffarnagar-251 001
and

W. U. MALIK

Kashmir University, Srinagar

Manuscript received 18 January 1982, revised 15 March 1983,
accepted 30 March 1983

INTERACTION between Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) with benzamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) has been reported earlier^{1,2}. The composition and structural characteristics of BTSC complex of Ag(I)

have since been studied and the results are reported here.

Experimental

Fresh solutions of BTSC³ and AgNO₃ were always used. The strength of AgNO₃ solution was determined by the usual method.

Conductometric titrations of BTSC against Ag(I) were carried out to determine the metal-ligand ratio. A series of solutions keeping BTSC concentration constant and varying [Ag⁺] (direct titration) and vice-versa (reverse titration) were prepared keeping the volume constant in each case. The plots of conductance vs concentration of metal (or ligand) gave inflections corresponding to the stoichiometric ratio. Philips conductivity bridge with dip type conductivity cell (cell constant 0.62) was used for determining the conductance.

Amperometric titrations were carried out on a manual polarograph in conjunction with a Pye Scalamp galvanometer. Both direct and reverse titrations were carried out using 2.0 × 10⁻² M solution of the metal and the ligand in presence of 0.2 M KNO₃ as supporting electrolyte and 0.008% gelatin as maximum suppressor. Solutions were deaerated with purified N₂ gas. The titrations were carried out at -0.1 volts applied on d.m.e. using SCE as reference electrode. The corrected values for dilution factor of current were plotted against the volume of metal or ligand. The inflection point gave the stoichiometric ratio.

Elico pH-meter using glass electrode in conjunction with SCE was used for pH-metric measurements. Standard solution of KOH was prepared in

double distilled CO_2 free water and pH titrations were performed at different constant temperatures, using Toshniwal thermostatic bath.

The silver complex was analysed and results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF COMPLEX
($\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{SO}$)Ag

Element	% Found	% Required	Element	% Found	% Required
Ag	34.0332	34.0330	N	17.6692	17.6680
C	30.2863	30.2828	O	5.0552	5.0480
H	2.8382	2.8395	S	10.0934	10.0960

The recrystallised complex was subjected to magnetic measurement at 31° with the help of Gouy's magnetic balance, having a semimicrometer balance, model 'C' Meltlov Zoric type H_{16} No. 140050. The ir spectral studies were carried out in KBr medium by the method of fast scanning using Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The silver complex was characterised by different physico-chemical methods. In all the cases sharp breaks corresponding to 1:1 metal-ligand were observed for both direct and reverse conductometric titrations.

Plateaux for BTSC was found to exist at -0.1 volt. Therefore a constant potential of -0.1 volt was applied for all the amperometric titrations. Normal curves were obtained and gave sharp breaks confirming the stoichiometric results of conductometric studies.

The pK (8.1) value for BTSC determined pH -metrically was in agreement with the value obtained polarographically². pH -titrations performed with mixtures of Ag(I) -BTSC, BTSC and Ag(I) separately against $0.1 M$ KOH showed lowering of pH , proving liberation of H^+ ions during complexation. Maximum lowering in the case of 1:1 mixture, and the inflection corresponding to 1 mole KOH:1 mole Ag(I) indicated 1:1 stoichiometry of the complex.

pH -titrations of BTSC alone and in the presence of different concentrations of Ag(I) ions keeping constant ionic strength ($0.2 M$) with KNO_3 performed according to the method of Calvin and Melchoir⁴ gave normal pH -metric curves when titrated against $0.1 M$ KOH. From the curve, \bar{n} values at various pH were determined for different sets and the corresponding values of free ligand (\bar{A}) were calculated. The values of \bar{n} were plotted against the corresponding values of pA or $-\log A$. The stability constants at $\bar{n}=0.5$ were found to be $\log \beta = 3.05$ at 25° (Fig. 1; curve 1) and $\log \beta = 2.85$ at 30° (Fig. 1; curve 2).

From the values of stability constants, free energy change, $\Delta G^\circ = -17.4027 \text{ kJ mole}^{-1}$, using relation

Fig. 1

$\Delta G^\circ = -2.303 RT \log \beta$; and enthalpy change, $\Delta H^\circ = -69.1549 \text{ kJ mole}^{-1}$, using relation $\log(\beta)_{T_2}/(\beta)_{T_1} = -\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{2.303R} (1/T_2 - 1/T_1)$; and entropy change $\Delta S^\circ = 173.70 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$, using relation $\Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta G^\circ - \Delta H^\circ}{T}$, were calculated.

It is inferred from these values that the reaction between Ag(I) and BTSC is exothermic and proceeds spontaneously as ΔH° and ΔG° are negative. Positive value of entropy favours complexation.

Results of chemical analysis (Table 1) further supported the stoichiometric ratio obtained from electrometric studies.

Ag(I) complex of BTSC has $4d^{10}$ configuration and was found to be diamagnetic.

The ir absorption band at 3280 cm^{-1} observed in the BTSC was due to NH and NH_2 stretching vibrations. In the Ag(I) complex, this band was shifted to higher frequency to 3390 cm^{-1} , suggesting that the NH_2 group of hydrazine was not involved in complex formation⁵.

The absorption bands occurring at $1318, 790$ and 760 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching. Similar assignments have been made for thioacetamide and other thio compounds^{6,7}. In Ag complex, these bands were shifted to lower wave lengths at 750 and 725 cm^{-1} , suggesting the involvement of sulphur in the binding to the metal⁸.

The appearance of the bending vibrations of the amino and amide groups in the same frequency at 1630 cm^{-1} in the complex and in the ligand indicated non-involvement of the amido nitrogen atom in the bonding. However, appearance of NCS bend frequencies occurring at $1170, 1035$ and 1100 cm^{-1} in Ag(I) complex indicated the participation of